

Relationship Between Students' Social Anxiety and their Self-Esteem at University Level

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Abstract

Social anxiety is a significant problem faced by students in general but at university level. This anxiety negatively affects students' self-esteem which motivated the scholars to investigate the relationship between students' social anxiety and their self-esteem. The focus was to investigate the level of students' social anxiety, their self-esteem level, and the relationship between them. Following null hypotheses, the researchers adopted quantitative correlational research design. Students at Universities in Malakand division of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa constituted the population and through simple random sampling techniques a sample group of 139 students constituted the sample group. The data obtained from the selected respondents through two questionnaires Students Social Anxiety Questionnaire (SSAQ) and Students' Self-esteem Questionnaire (SSQ). Both these questionnaires were pilot tested to ensure reliability, and its content validity was measured through expert opinions. The collected data was analyzed through descriptive and inferential statistics through SPSS software. The results revealed that average level of social anxiety among students was found, and a high-level of self-esteem was calculated for the students. Furthermore, the results also showed a positive but low correlation between students' social anxiety and their self-esteem. Based on these results, it was concluded that students are afraid of different social situations including social interactions, making friends and trust on others. Therefore, the researcher recommended the families of all students, to socially interact their children to build their social skills and to the end of their fear and weakness in front of strangers. The researcher mostly recommended to the teacher to involves the students of different curricula, extracurricular activity, and co-Caracalla activities.

Keywords: Social Anxiety; Self-Esteem; Generalized Anxiety Disorder; Stress Disorder

INTRODUCTION

Current life in this world is full of challenges and therefore, human beings are also supposed to be prepared for the uncertain and unexpected challenges in this contemporary life. Furthermore, for students in their academic lives, they are facing new challenges and expectations that sometimes negatively affect their academic activities. Among these challenges social anxiety is also an important one that affects their live from multiple perspectives. According to Murad (2020) social anxiety is a physiological disorder, furthermore, social anxiety is a dominant emotion disorder which is frequently found among

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youngster in early ages. This leads to different behavioral and psychological disorders i.e., the people of social anxiety feel fear, shy, nervousness, apprehension, fear uncombed could not perform the social interaction to the other.

Similarly, Izgiç (2004) recently added while studying social anxiety, that several cases have been reported every day and desperation leads to different forms of social phobia. It is not a new phenomenon, but it is the old physiological disorder of anxiety people. According to Health (2013) added from gender perspectives that social anxiety among females is higher than male and it is a common type of anxiety disorders in which the people of anxiety feel fear of different situation for example speaking to the front of people, meetings, or job interview. According to Alesi, Rappo, and Pepi (2012) self-esteem is the personal psychological characteristic that the person relating the self-judgment based on the one's values about human, and Schunk (1985) believed that self-esteem implies to the value of people, emotion evaluating and of itself worth about human.

Anxiety is an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, worried thoughts, and physical changes like increased blood pressure. People with anxiety disorders usually have recurring intrusive thoughts or concerns. They may avoid certain situations out of worry. They may also have physical symptoms such as sweating, trembling, dizziness, or a rapid heartbeat. According to the Higuera (3rd Sep 2018) Social anxiety disorder is the disorder of individual in which the person feel extreme fear in a social setting. Due to extreme Fear the individual must trouble talking to people, do not face new people and do not attend the social gathering. The fear over come to the individual mind, and they cannot perform basic activity. They look like shy but the difference between shy and social anxiety as the social anxiety is the long-term processes and the shyness the short term.

The patient of social anxiety effects the individual work, attend the school, develop the close relationship with the people an also their family. According to the (Anxiety and Depression Association of Amarica ADAA, 2018) approximately 15 million American adults have a social anxiety disorder patient in which the patient age starts to the 13-year-old which the social anxiety disorder symptoms are seen. The physical symptoms of social anxiety which according (Anxiety and Depression Association of Amarica ADAA, 2018) the patient of social anxiety shy everyone. They cannot face the social or family people. When they in trouble or problem excessive sweating in body. When they face the stranger people or relative, they have speaking problem the think one word but said another word. Due to the high pressure or fear the individual dizziness and lightshades in the body. The heartbeat of the patient is too fast due to the fear. 2.4 types of social anxiety the psychological symptoms (Anxiety and Depression Association of Amarica ADAA, 2018).The patient of social anxiety disorder worrying intensely about the social situations. They cannot participate all the time. They cannot go to events avoiding the social situations. Your self-stable side to the social interaction and worrying about other people will notice you are stressed or nervous.

According to George Crile (1921) the panic attack as suddenly feeling of fear and uncontrolled feeling about something which cause the panic attack physical symptoms as racing heartbeat, fast breathing, and sweating. People become fearful of those attack which cause the panic anxiety disorder. Panic anxiety disorder unreasonable feelings or some things that fear and strong physical reaction that the individual reached to the peak of motion due to the suddenly fear. Causes of panic disorder is panic attack the experts experience that panic attack develop

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the panic anxiety disorder. the brain and nerve system play the key role of fear anxiety which increases the panic anxiety disorder Family history play the role of panic anxiety disorder the social interaction of his family is brief. Another is mental health issue such that depression. Sometime the panic anxiety disorder causes the substance abuse problem alcoholism and drugs increase the panic attack According to (Mental Health Information, n.d.) the patient of PAD is sudden and repeated panic attack of different fear which the patient reached to the peak of motion. The felling of individual is uncontrolled due to fear. All the time worry about when the next panic attack will happen. Fast heartbeat, sweating and tumbling body and the physical symptoms of PAD. According to (chief) the treatment of PAD is to increases or improve the function of in our daily life. PAD treat both Psychotherapy and medication. Psychotherapy also called talk therapy that the experts know the problem, thoughts of individual through the psychotherapy. Another treatment of PAD medication that the doctor gives the drugs to the patient for treatment. Medical treatment as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) safe with the insignificant risk of serious effect which recommended the drugs f fluoxetine (Prozac), paroxetine (Paxil, Pexeva) and sertraline (Zoloft). Benzodiazepines these Sedative and control the nerve system.

According to (Anxiety and Depression Association of Amarica ADAA, 2018) some the individual have some flashbacks, intensive memory, some events, than the individual have suffering trouble and think about that what was the next happen they can feel more stress about these situation Basically ((PTSD) is a serious potentiality anxiety disorder in which Cause due to the serious issue condition such that human nature disaster, accidents, suddenly death of someone than the patient suffer more stress about these conditions. According to (Anxiety and Depression Association of Amarica ADAA, 2018) Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) are those type of anxiety disorder in which the person takes more stress about issues, event, or some situation. The stress includes the violent, personal problem, natural and human disaster, accident, or the military problems.

(PTSD) cause some personal relation such that when the close friend or relative cause death than the patient take increased stress about the accident currently in America about eight million people in United States living in (PTDC). It is the most common disorder in children in teens accident to the (national child trumatic stress network, 2011) shows the symptoms of the patients. They explain that how the child was judge due to the physical reaction who is suffering the (PTSD) disorder. Most times the (PTAD) cause the flashback memory in which the patient takes more stress about them. In the age of teens, the people have passed the stage of love. If the individual is failure in love. Then the disorder of PTSD cause because they take more stress about the breakup. Due to flashback the individuals anytime thinking about something. Sitting side alone, they do not talk too much, and they have mood changer experts. According to Bhandari (2022) (PTSD) disorder can be treated by both therapy and medication (PTSD) Therapy has three main goals such that improve symptoms, teach skill I deal them, and restore the self-esteem. During the therapy session give 60 to 90 to the patient to treat eth disorder. And if the therapy does not work than give the medicine.

The concept of Self-esteem

The concept of self-esteem in which the individuals have positive or negative attitude towards oneself, as well as the overall assessment of one worth. People inspire due to the high self-esteem which implies positive and courteous manner rather than negative self-

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esteem or ego. The self-esteem is one of the only self-concept which define the Rosenberg 06 Nov (2021) totally felling and thoughts of individual reapers the object himself. Beside self-esteem is one of the aspects of proficiency and self-identity. The concept of self-esteem may be misleading and used than the result of its extensive use is everyday language and popular psychology.as a result uses of the scale should be aware with the scientific study of the concept of self-esteem and its difficulties. The book by Rosenberg is a fantastic place to start. There are thousands of empirical investigations and theoretical assessments of this term in the academic literature as well as various definition and measurement to self-esteem in the social sciences. The result of Rosenberg work that how social structural position lick racial or ethnic statuses and institutional context like families and schools relate to the self-esteem. Here the structure of social forces provided the characteristics set of experience which are actively interpreted the individual of self-concept shaped. The four keys of theoretical principal of self-concept were reflected appraisals, social comparison, self-attributions, and psychological centrality.

Self-esteem examining the outcomes commonly encourage as an individual or various in addition to the result of social influences. All the time we can remember that self-esteem is the stable general characteristic of adults not easily manipulate the outcome of experimental design. According to (Tomaka, 1993) indict that experimentally manipulating source of familiar and un failure have to any measurable impact against a lifetime of self-evaluative experience” the thinking of self-esteem unrealistic but self-esteem is taught it real, but it is developed the life experience of individual.

Self-esteem

According to Boyde (2014) the addition of self-esteem is a critical factor in personal well-being because the additional self-esteem in positive relationship and negative self-esteem builds the negative relationship in the individual. According to (James, 1890) self-esteem is the subjective measure of personal value and worth that all the Individual have change and unique perspective and believes. Likewise, according to (Alesi, Rappo, & Pepi (2012) self-esteem is regarded the personal psychological characteristic that the person relating the self-judgment based on the one's values about human, and Schunk (1985) believed that self-esteem implies to the value of people, emotion evaluating and of itself worth about human. According to the researchers there are distinct types of self-esteem that includes low self-esteem, high self-esteem. Low self-esteem is those in which the person has lack of confidence about who they are and what they can do. They can never trust itself in any situation. They think incomplete about itself. Every situation the afraid about making mistake because what the people think about him. Fell negative about itself. Self-esteem has two type's low self-esteem and high self-esteem.

According to Firestone (2019) low self-esteem refers the lack of confidence in individual and felling badly about oneself. The people of low self-esteem feel unlovable, awkward, or incomplete about yourself. According to the researcher Morris Rosenberg 06 Nov (2021) people of low self-esteem tend to be hypersensitive. Low self-esteem is those in which the person has lack of confidence about who they are and what they can do. They can never trust itself in any situation. They think incomplete about itself. Every situation the afraid about making mistake because what the people think about him. Fell negative about itself. The

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individual of low self-esteem cannot say anything with the assert most of the time they are blaming itself when the thing going wrong. When something happens good, they think the credit for every success goes to luck. All the time they never trust yourself and self-confidence. When the see others, they are comparing yourself I am with like you and stop struggling .in life when they are failure. They stop struggle about problem or situation

High self-esteem mean that the individual believes in yourself and know that only self can remove your weakness, but they have a lot of strength which really shape the individual life. High self-esteem is the opposite of low self-esteem. High self-esteem holding itself in positive regard. Generally affording yourself love, value, dignity, and respect. They love everything and think any perspective I am perfect. The high self-esteem the person has a lot of quality of thinking and good felling of yourself. High self-esteem is a frame of mind that the person celebrates the strengths and challenge the weakness of every situation. They feel good about itself and its life.

The individual of high self-esteem all the time they are believing yourself and confident When some going on they know what they want and need. The set their future because they know about yourself and success. All the time they have effective communication skill and effective voice tune for others mostly enjoying they are enjoying healthy relationship because they have a great mind set, they are goal oriented focused on self-improvement if any problem they face they laugh and laughing because they can solve easily. They are taking care yourself i.e., physically, emotionally, and mentally. They are believing yourself.

According to Kaiser (2022) motivating the students all level students such that elementary, college and university level students take a combination of factor both school and home setting. There is the certain factor that effect the self-esteem of student. Some effects play the confidence roll of student self-esteem such that including the type of relationship thy build their teacher, interpersonal relation with their peers and advocacy that the student received at home. Individual attestation and engaging environment will all play roll of the confidence of self-esteem of student.

The teacher attitude is direct affect the student self-esteem if a student has often quickly sense and the teacher is not engaged the student in class. Mostly the condescending attitudes, an impersonal attitude and favoritism can affect the class student and they learn negative fashion of self-esteem. Good teacher is representing and encourage their student to build the self-esteem and awareness. Individual feedback is also important such that the teacher care the student performance. Some students have academic and behavioral problem they play the dynamic affect the student self-esteem foe example some students have less knowledge about some topic and the faculty question the deep knowledge the students answer was wrong this time the student self-esteem affect. some students affect due to the other student bullied attitude which play bad roll in class which effect the self-esteem of student.

Self-esteem in student not only effect the school setting or their home setting but also effect the student ambition. If the home family do not encourage the student than the self-esteem of the student will be low, and they are losing of incrust the study of student life. Sometime the student having pass the excellent grades, but the teacher encourages the other student during this time the self-esteem of the student was low and affect the student performance. There is the negative relation of social anxiety and self-esteem among the student which the social anxiety affects the student self-esteem and peak to lower stage such that if one student

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has psychological anxiety disorder and the teacher discourage the student than the student self-esteem reached to the low self-esteem.

Problem Statement

Keeping the above discussion and current increases in general masses anxiety. This study includes to investigate the relationship between social anxiety and self-esteem among the university level students.

Research objectives

Keeping in view the research problem the follow research objectives were formulated.

1. To find out the level of social anxiety among the university level.
2. To find out the self-esteem among the university level.
3. To find out relationship between social anxiety and self-esteem.

Research Hypotheses

Now a days the twenty first (21) century the university students face a lot of psychological Problems. Which effect the student academic life in this study the researcher investigates the level of social anxiety and self-esteem among the university student and finding the relation of social anxiety and self-esteem the university student.

Delimitations of the study

The researcher delimited the study to the University of Swat due to the lake of resources and financially issue. The researcher further de limit the study to some specific department the university of swat because the total population of the university is 6030 it was impossible for the researcher to collect data all of them for this purpose the researcher further delimit the study to specific department which include the department of Islamic study, education, Pakistan study and management (BBA) department are selected for the data collection.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Previous literature study the scholar used the quantitative nature of design because the data collection of the study was statistically than also the researcher finding out the result statistically, to use the quantitative design research. That is way the Quantitative design suitable or this study.

Research Population

The researcher selected the University of Swat for the data collection, the total population of the University of Swat is 6031 in 35 program degree. But the researcher selects the 1-degree program for the pilot study which selected from the social sciences in five programs for actual study which to the applied science.

Sample and sampling technique

The population of the study was delimited to five department students at university of Swat which includes one. Department of Psychological studies, 2. Department of Zoology, 3.

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Microbiology, 4. Center for Management and commerce, and 5. Department of Chemistry. From all these departments a total of 160 respondents were selected through simple random sampling techniques. But only 139 students filled the questionnaires. So therefore, the total number of the sample group respondents were 139 BS students.

Data collection tool

The researcher collect data through questionnaire which included thirty-three items to measure the social anxiety and self-esteem among the university students. The social anxiety item is twenty-three and the self-esteem item is ten to finding out the result. The scale of social anxiety is Willoughby social anxiety scale, and the scale of self-esteem is Rosenberg self-esteem scale. These two scale the researcher finding out the relationship between social anxiety and self-esteem among the university students. For the social anxiety option Always (1), usually (2), somewhat (3), Never (4). Furthermore, for the self-esteem scale the option include strongly agree (1), agree, disagree (2), strongly (3) disagree (4).

Reliability and Validity

The researcher finds out the through the polite study the reliability co-efficient of the data collection scale. The reliability co-efficient of the data collection scale of social anxiety was .785 and for self-esteem questionnaire the α value = .812 which was acceptable for the social are applied science according to Graiffee (2012). Therefore, the questionnaires were trusted and were administered to the sample group respondents. Furthermore, the researcher checked the validity of the data collection scale through Dr. Nasir Ahmad they checked the validity of the scale and pass out the scale to start the collection of data to the students.

Data analysis

The researcher placed the collected data into SPSS 26. The collected data were analyzed through descriptive statistics like percentages, frequencies, Mean scores, and Standard deviations. However, to measure the relationship between the selected variables the researcher followed Pearson correlation test.

Analysis and Results

Table 1.1 representation of male and female respondents in the sample group

Respondents		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Male	99	71.2	71.2
	Female	40	28.8	28.8
	Total	139	100.0	100.0

Table 1.1 revealed the gender-wise details of the sample group participants. According to the above table 99 respondents were male and forty respondents were female. The percentages of male respondents were 71.2% and for female it was 28.8%. Therefore, it was concluded that majority of the study respondents were male having 71% representation.

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Table 1.2 Program-wise details of the study participants

Department	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Microbiology	64	46.0	46.0	46.0
BBA	16	11.5	11.5	57.6
Chemistry	12	8.6	8.6	66.2
Psychology	13	9.4	9.4	75.5
Zoology	34	24.5	24.5	100.0
Total	139	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.2 showed the program-wise detail of the respondent. According to the above table the frequency of the respondent of microbiology were sixty-four in the given study. The percentage of the microbiology was 46.0% the valid present was also same 46.0% and the cumulative percent of the microbiology were 46.0%. The second department was BBA in the give study which the frequency of the respondent was sixteen in which the percentage of the BBA was 11.5%, the valid percentage was also same 11.5% and the cumulative percentage of the BBA were 57.6%. The third department was chemistry in which the frequency of the respondents was sixteen. The percentage of the chemistry was 8.6%, the valid percentage was also same 8.6% and the cumulative percentage were 66.2%. The fourth department was psychology in which the frequency of the respondents was thirty-four, the percentage of the psychology was 9.4% the valid percentage was also same 9.4% and the cumulative percentage of the psychology were 75%. The final program- wise detail of the respondent to the above table was zoology in which the frequency of the respondents was thirty-four the percentage of the zoology was 24.5% the valid percentage was also same 24.5% and the cumulative percentage were 100%. Therefore, it was concluded the high frequency respondent department was microbiology in which the frequency of the respondent was 64.the percentage were 46.0% and the cumulative percentage were 46.0%. The lowest frequency department was chemistry in which the frequency of the respondent was 16.the percentage was 9.4% and cumulative percentage was 75.5%.

Table No 1.3 Social Anxiety

S#	Social Anxiety	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Feeling Anxious and the social people	2.6414	1.05556
2	Feeling Self-Anxious	2.9040	1.00693
3	Anxious In working time	2.8596	1.41402
4	Lacking confidence due to anxious	2.8129	1.05024

Table 1.3 intimate the responses of students on their social anxiety aspects. Item number 1, 2, 3, and 4 mean scores 2.6414, 2.9040, 2.8596, and 2.8129 with SD 1.05556, 1.00693, 1.41402, and 1.05024 showed that respondents were agreed that they usually feeling get anxious in from of strangers, worried to feeling self-Anxious, all of the time Anxious in working time when other People watched them These results reflects that majority of the

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students get anxious in different social interactions.

Table no 1.4 Self-Esteem

S#	Self-Esteem	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Individuals feel a prominent level of self-Esteem	2.8518	1.30617
2	Individual feel positive Self-Esteem	2.9597	1.29357

Table 1.4 intimate the responses of students on their Self-Esteem aspects. Item number 1 and 2 mean scores 2.8518 and 2.9597 with SD 1.30617 and 1.29357 showed that respondents were agreed that they usually feeling a high and positive level of Self-Esteem. All the time students satisfied with himself.

Table 1.5 Relationship between social anxiety and self-esteem of students at university level

Relationship Social Anxiety and self-Esteem		Social anxiety	self-esteem
Social anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	.177*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.037
	N	139	139
self-esteem	Pearson Correlation	.177*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037	
	N	139	139

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The above table showed the relationship between students' social anxiety and their self-esteem. The r value .177 and the sig value .037 showed that there is small but significant relationship between the two variables of this study. Furthermore, it was concluded that students face social anxiety during the university life education which affects the self-esteem, and both are positive correlation.

FINDINGS

1. The results of mean score of first five items were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing most of the respondents were socially anxious as they were usually afraid of heights, afraid of different things, and can be easily hurt by others.
2. The mean score 2.48 reflected that student can explain their moods easily, very few students showed that they cannot explain their mood in some situations.
3. The results of mean score of six items were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing most of the respondents were socially anxious as they were feeling incomparable meet with new people, daydream frequently include in fantasies not involving concrete situation, discourage easily, say thing haste, and then regard them, disturb with the new presence and the cry easily.
4. The results of mean score of last five items of social anxiety were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing the majority of the respondents were socially anxious as they were usually bother when people watch even they work do well, criticism hurt them badly, feel miserable, hesitate to voluntary in discussion or debates in group of people, they have sense of isolation either the alone or group of people and they usually self-conscious before superior.

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5. The mean score of items no 14th is 2.57 are closed to the range of the than they reflected that student sometime could hurt badly to the criticism.
6. The results of mean score of last five items of social anxiety were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing most of the respondents were socially anxious as they were usually lack confidence self-conscious, scared with blood, feel other people better than us and it will be hard for them to make a mind. Likewise, the results of mean score of first five items were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing most of the respondents were high self-esteem as they were agreed person of worth, have number of qualities, can do anything, and cannot feel proud too much.
7. The result of item no third the mean score 2.28 reflected that they were strongly disagree that they cannot feel that I am a failure. Furthermore, the results of mean score of 7, 8, and 10 items were in the range of 3.51 to 2.50 showing most of the respondents were high self-esteem as they were agreed satisfied with self, wish more respect for himself, think we are good at all. Similarly, the result of item no sixth the mean score 3.46 reflected that they most of the participant were strongly agreed that they take positive attitude toward his self. On the contrary, the result of item no ninth the mean score 2.47 reflected that they majority of the participant were disagree that they cannot feel useless at times.
8. The r value of .177 which was significant at .037 showed positive but low correlations between students' social anxiety and their self-esteem.

Conclusions

Based on the above findings of the study the following conclusions were drawn.

Students interacts with each other in the state of fear because they were unable to cope with the social situations. This fear is often in the form of heights, fooling/bullying in educational institutions. Furthermore, the students were usually not in the position to explain their own state of mode that shows a prominent level of mistrust on self, which decline their self-esteem.

Students were socially anxious they cannot feel comfortable to the front of new buddy or people, they were not face the new people due to the respect of new peoples or they feel fear from them therefore most of the time they see day dream frequently which have not a specific or concrete situation, when someone criticized them they discourage easily regard lialbit thing make them a big problem for himself similarly they disturbed with the new presence because the feel uncomparable in the front of peoples and most of the time they cry easily in any situation.

To the above study of social anxiety majority of the students were socially anxious they were lack their confidence of some critical situation i.e., when they see blood or injuries of someone they cannot face them they were loosed their confidence easily most of the time they feel other people is batter then us which can be lose the confidence of the individual and it were be very difficult or hard them to make our mind batter.

To the above study Students have low self-esteem due to most of the students feel they were the person of worth that is they have a lot of qualities of different aspect when other people can do the always can be do and most of the time, they feel proud for himself. But the one aspect t of the self -esteem, was that the indusial of the self-esteem of the give study cannot feel that I am failure they do anything.

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Student of the self-esteem of the given study they were satisfied with himself most of the time they wish take more respect for himself due to his goodness because they feel good at all the time for self and others. But most of the students wish to take the positive towards itself and all the time the students cannot feel useless at the time, most the time they were face anything.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions following recommendations were made.

1. The university teachers are recommended to work on the self-esteem of students by identifying them the opportunities of self-expressing in the form of departmental co-curricular activities.
2. Furthermore, teachers and administration may also provide a conducive learning environment so that the negative impacts of social anxiety may be reduced. Furthermore, the stakeholders may also make arrangement for academic counselling mechanisms for students.
3. Additionally, there may also be close coordination between students, teachers, and students' parents so that they collectively work on the personality development of students.
4. It was further recommended to the high ups of teachers to arrange workshops and trainings for the teachers to orient and sensitize them about classroom emotional abusive practices which is one the significant sources of social anxiety.
5. Furthermore, studies may be conducted at primary, secondary and at college level on students' social anxiety and their self-esteem, which will provide enough data for the policy makers to design such policy and educational atmosphere that could enhance the self-esteem of students and could reduce their social anxiety.

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